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TRANSDERMAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM AN OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The conventional oral dosage forms have some drawbacks like poor bioavailability, first pass metabolism, of drug, frequent dosing which may leads to patient non compliance. The transdermal drug delivery system is one of the type novel drug delivery system which overcome the problems arises from conventional dosage forms. A transdermal patch is medicated adhesive patch these is place on the surface of skin and these deliver a specific dose of drug medicament through the skin and in to bloodstream. It also helps to healing to a mild injured surface of skin. An advantage of a transdermal drug delivery route over other types of medication delivery such as oral, topical, intravenous, intramuscular, etc. is that the patch provides a controlled release of the medication into the patient and it gives painless drug delivery to the patient over intravenous route of drug administration. Its having some disadvantage it permit only drug having smaller molecular size. This review gives valuable information about the TDDS like its advantages, disadvantages, types of TDDS, different methods for formulation of transdermal patches, different evaluation of transdermal patches. Different methods for preparation of transdermal patches. Skin permeation enhancement techniques have been developed to improve the bioavailability of drug.

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INTRODUCTION

The development of a novel delivery system for existing drug molecules not only improves the drug's performance in terms of efficacy and safety but also improves patient compliance and overall therapeutic benefit to a significant extent. Transdermal therapeutic systems are defined as self-contained, discrete dosage forms which, applied to the intact skin, deliver the drug through the skin at a controlled rate to the systemic circulation. When the main objective of transdermal drug delivery system is to deliver drugs into systemic circulation through skin at predetermined rate with minimal inter and intra patient variation. Currently transdermal delivery is one of the most promising methods for drug application. It enhances patient compliances and minimizes harmful side effects of a drug. Like gastrointestinal incompatibility caused from temporary over dose and is convenience drug delivery system. That will improve bioavailability, more uniform plasma levels, longer duration of action resulting in a reduction in dosing frequency, reduced side effects and improved therapy due to maintenance of plasma levels up to the end of the dosing interval compared to a decline in plasma levels with conventional oral dosage forms. causes undesirable side effects. Several important advantages of transdermal drug delivery are limitations of hepatic first pass metabolism, enhancement of therapeutic efficacy and maintenance of steady plasma level of drug. The transdermal route has become one of the most successful and innovative drug delivery systems for research in pharmaceutical sciences. Transdermal drug delivery provides a leading edge over injectables and oral routes by increasing Patient compliance and avoiding first pass metabolism respectively. Transdermal drug delivery is not only provides controlled, constant administration of the drug ,but also allows continuous input of drugs with short biological half lives and eliminates pulsed entry into systemic circulation. The first transdermal patch was approved in 1981 for the relief of motion sickness, nausea and vomiting. The transdermal drug delivery market was until recently, solely based on passive patch technology that relied on simple diffusion across the skin.

Advantages of Transdermal drug Delivery system.

- Steady state permeation of drug across the skin will maintain the desired drug level in blood.
- It is one of alternative drug delivery system for patients who can't able to tolerate oral dosage forms.
- In which possible administer the drug in unconscious patients by using the TDDS.
- Those drugs provide the irritation to the GIT, produces nausea, vomiting and other GIT disturbances can be used in TDDS which is avoid the direct effects of the drug on stomach & intestine.
- In transdermal therapy Sustained drug delivery is possible.
- First pass metabolism of Drug has been eliminated in TDDS.
- The frequency of dose administration is minimized in TDDS.
- Self administration of drug is possible in TDDS.
- TDDS are non-invasive which avoids many problems in parenteral therapy.
- It is one of the painless and easy drug administration systems.
- The drugs with short half life and narrow therapeutic index are the best candidates for TDDS.

Disadvantages of Transdermal drug delivery system.

- In TDDS some patients develop contact dermatitis at the site of application.
- Only potent drugs are suitable candidates for transdermal patch because of the natural limits of drug entry is limited.
- Some drugs e.g. scopolamine transdermal patch placed behind the ear, it is uncomfortable to the patient.
- In TDDS Long time adherence of patch is difficult.
- The transdermal patch having high manufacturing cost as compare to conventional dosage form.
- TDDS cannot deliver ionic drugs through the skin.
- TDDS cannot achieve high drug levels in blood/plasma.
- Cannot develop TDDS for drugs of large molecular size.
- Cannot develop TDDS, if drug or formulation causes irritation to skin.

Limitation of TDDS

- The drug moiety must possess some physicochemical properties for penetration through skin and if dose of drug is large i.e. more than 10-25mg/day transdermal delivery is very difficult. daily dose of drug preferred less than 5mg/day.
- Local irritation at the site of administration such as itching, erythema and local edema may be caused by drug or the excipients used in the formulations.
- Clinical need is another area that has to be examined carefully before a decision is made to develop a transdermal product.
- Some patients develop contact dermatitis at the site of application due to system components.
- The barrier function of the skin changes from one site to another, from person to person and with age.
- Poor skin permeability limits the number of drugs that can be delivered in this manner.
- Tolerance inducing drugs or those (e.g., hormones) requiring chronopharmacological management is not suitable candidates.

Anatomy of skin:

1. The epidermis
2. The viable epidermis
3. A non-viable epidermis (*Stratum corneum*)
4. The overlying dermis

The Epidermis:

The epidermis is a continually self-renewing, stratified squamous epithelium covering the entire outer surface of the body and primarily composed of two parts: the living or viable cells of the malpighian layer (viable epidermis) and the dead cells of the *stratum corneum* commonly referred to as the horny layer 5. Viable epidermis is further classified into four distinct layers as shown in

- *Stratum lucidum*
- *Stratum granulosum*
- *Stratum spinosum*
- *Stratum basale*

FIG. 1: SCHEMATIC REPRESENTATION OF ANATOMY OF SKIN.

Stratum corneum:

This is the outermost layer of skin also called as horny layer. It is the rate limiting barrier that restricts the inward and outward movement of chemical substances. The barrier nature of the horny layer depends critically on its constituents: 75-80% proteins, 5-15% lipids, and 5-10% undansetron material on a dry weight basis. *Stratum corneum* is approximately 10 mm thick when dry but swells to several times when fully hydrated. It is flexible but relatively impermeable. The architecture of horny layer (figure 3) may be modeled as a wall-like structure with protein bricks and lipid mortar. It consists of horny skin cells (corneocytes) which are connected via desmosomes (protein-rich appendages of the cell membrane). The corneocytes are embedded in a lipid matrix which plays a significant role in determining the permeability of substance across the skin.

SCHEMATIC REPRESENTATION OF MICROSTRUCTURE OF STRATUM CORNEUM**Viable epidermis:**

This is situated beneath the *stratum corneum* and varies in thickness from 0.06 mm on the eyelids to 0.8mm on the palms. Going inwards, it consists of various layers as *stratum lucidum*, *stratum granulosum*, *stratum spinosum*, and the *stratum basale*. In the basale layer, mitosis of the cells constantly renews the epidermis and this proliferation compensates the loss of dead horny cells from the skin surface. As the cells produced by the basale layer move outward, they themselves alter morphologically and histochemically, undergoing keratinization to form the outermost layer of *stratum corneum*.

Dermis:

Dermis is the layer of skin just beneath the epidermis which is 3 to 5 mm thick layer and is composed of a matrix of connective tissues, which contains blood vessels, lymph vessels, and nerves. The cutaneous blood supply has essential function in regulation of body temperature. It also provides nutrients and oxygen to the skin, while removing toxins and waste products. Capillaries reach to within 0.2 mm of skin surface and provide sink conditions for most molecules penetrating the skin barrier. The blood supply thus keeps the dermal concentration of permeate very low, and the resulting concentration difference across the epidermis provides the essential driving force for transdermal permeation. In terms of transdermal drug delivery, this layer is often viewed as essentially gelled water, and thus provides a minimal barrier to the delivery of most polar drugs, although the dermal barrier may be significant when delivering highly lipophilic molecules.

Hypodermis:

The hypodermis or subcutaneous fat tissue supports the dermis and epidermis. It serves as a fat storage area. This layer helps to regulate temperature, provides nutritional support and mechanical protection. It carries principal blood vessels and nerves to skin and may contain sensory pressure organs. For transdermal drug delivery, drug has to penetrate through all three layers and reach in systemic circulation.

BASIC COMPONENT OF TRANSDERMAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM**Polymer matrix or matrices:**

Polymers are the foundation of transdermal system. The selection of polymer and design are of prime importance. Considerations for polymer selection in transdermal delivery system:

- Should be stable and non-reactive with the drug moiety.
- Easily available, fabricated and manufactured in to desired formulations.
- The properties of polymer e.g. molecular weight glass transition temperature. Melting point and chemical functionality etc. should be such that drug can easily diffused through it and with other components of system.
- Mechanical properties should not change if large amount of drug incorporate.
- Should provide consistent release of drug throughout the life of system. The polymers used in transdermal system are.

Natural Polymers:

e.g. zein, gelatin cellulose derivatives, gums, natural rubber, shellac etc.

Synthetic Elastomers:

e.g. hydri rubber, polyisobutylene, polybutadiene, acrylonitrile etc.

Synthetic Polymers:

e.g. polyvinylchloride, polyethylene, polyvinyl alcohol, polypropylene, etc

Polymers used in transdermal system in versatile manner such as:**Rate controlling membrane:**

It control the release of drug by disperse through an inert polymer matrix. The polymer powder blended with drug moiety by physical manner and then moulded in to desired shape with required thickness and surface area.

Adhesive:

Make an intimate contact between the skin and transdermal system. It carries the drug which is dissolved or dispersed in solution or suspension form. The quality of drug diffused in to skin depending on the holding power.

Pressure sensitive adhesive:

Hitherto the rapidity of transdermal system can be done by pressure sensitive adhesive. The three most commonly used adhesives are polyisobutylene, polyacrylate and silicones in TDD devices

Release liners:

The patch is covered by protective liner during storage until it is used. The release liner removed and discarded just before the application of patch over the skin since release liner is in intimate contact with the transdermal system hence it should be physically as well as chemically inert. The release liner is composed of a base layer which may be non-occlusive (e.g. paper fabric) or occlusive (e.g. polyethylene, polyvinylchloride) and a release coating layer made up of silicon or Teflon. Other materials used as release liner in transdermal patches include polyester foil and metalized laminate.

Backing laminate:

While design the baking layer following points must be in consideration:

- Must be flexible.
- Should be compatible with transdermal system as remain in use while applying.
- Should be chemical resistance.
- Having good tensile strength.
- Non irritant

Examples of backings laminate are polyethylene film, polyester film, and polyolefin film.

Drug:

Transdermal delivery of drugs has taken a surge of popularity nowadays. Various physicochemical, pharmacokinetic and pharmacological properties of the drug should be considered for transdermal system development.

- ✓ Drug should have higher first pass metabolism.
- ✓ Drugs having narrow therapeutic window.
- ✓ Drugs with short half life.
- ✓ Drugs with frequent dosing.
- ✓ Low molecular weight moieties (<1000 Dalton)
- ✓ Drugs with low dose (mg/day).
- ✓ Low melting point substances (<200°C)
- ✓ Drugs having affinity with both lipophilic and hydrophilic phases.
- ✓ Drugs without any dermatological effect are suitable for formulation as transdermal patch.

Penetration enhancers:

Compounds which promote the penetration of topically applied drugs are commonly referred as absorption promoters, accelerants, or. penetration enhancers. Penetration enhancers are incorporated into a formulation to improve the diffusivity and solubility of drugs through the skin that would reversibly. reduce the barrier resistance of the skin.

Desired properties for penetration enhancers:

1. It should be non-irritant, non-sensitizing, nonphototoxic, and non-comedogenic.
2. Have no pharmacological activity in the body i.e. should not bind to the receptor site.
3. The accelerants should be chemically and physically compatible with all drugs and adjuvants to be formulated in topical preparations and devices.
4. It should have a desired solubility parameter that approximates that of skin.
5. It should be pharmacologically inert within the body, either locally or systemically.
6. It should not irritate or induce allergic responses.
7. The enhancer should work rapidly with a predictable onset of action.
8. The penetration enhancer should work unidirectional, i.e. should allow medicaments to enter the body while preventing the release of endogenous materials.

Other excipients:**Plasticizers:**

Plasticizers have also been used in many formulations ranging from 5 to 20% (w/w, dry basis). Along with the brittleness and ductility of the film, it is also responsible for adhesiveness of the film with other surfaces or membranes and improvement in strength of film. Some of its examples are glycerol or sorbitol, at 15%,w/w, dry basis, phosphate, phthalate esters, fatty acid esters and glycol derivatives such as PEG 200, and PEG 400.

Solvents:

Various solvents such as methanol, chloroform, acetone, isopropanol and dichloromethane etc. are used to prepare drug reservoir.

Methods for preparation of Transdermal patches:**Asymmetric TPX membrane method: -**

A prototype patch can be fabricated using a heat sealable polyester film with a concave of 1 cm diameter will be used as the backing membrane. Drug sample is dispensed into concave membrane, covered by TPX {poly- (4- methyl-1-pentene)} asymmetric membrane, and sealed by an adhesive.

Circular Teflon mould method: -

Solutions containing polymers in various ratios are used in an organic solvent. Calculated amount of drug is dissolved in half the quantity of same organic solvent. Enhancers in different concentrations are dissolved in the other half of the organic solvent and then added. Di-N butyl phthalate is added as a plasticizer into drug polymer solution. The total contents are stirred for 12 h and poured into circular Teflon mould. The moulds are placed on a leveled surface and covered with inverted funnel to control solvent vaporization in a laminar flow hood model with an air speed of 0.5 m/s. The solvent is allowed to evaporate for 24 h. The dried films are stored for another 24 h at $25\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a desiccators containing silica gel before evaluation to eliminate aging effects.

Mercury substrate method: -

In this method, drug is dissolved in polymer solution along with plasticizer. The above solution is to be stirred for 10-15 min to produce a homogenous dispersion and poured in to a leveled mercury surface, covered with inverted funnel to control solvent evaporation.

“IPM membranes” method: -

In this method, drug is dispersed in a mixture of water and propylene glycol containing carbomer 940 polymer and stirred for 12 h in magnetic stirrer. The dispersion is to be neutralized and made viscous by the addition of triethanolamine. Buffer pH 7.4 can be used in order to obtain solution gel, if the drug solubility in aqueous solution is very poor. The formed gel will be incorporated in the IPM membrane.

“EVAC membranes” method: -

In order to prepare the target transdermal therapeutic system, 1% carbopol reservoir gel, polyethylene (PE), ethylene vinyl acetate copolymer (EVAC) membranes can be used as rate control membranes. If the drug is not soluble in water, propylene glycol is used for the preparation of gel. Drug is dissolved in propylene glycol; carbopol resin will be added to the above solution and neutralized by using 5% w/w sodium hydroxide solution. The drug (in gel form) is placed on a sheet of backing layer covering the specified area. A rate controlling membrane is placed over the gel and the edges are sealed by heat to obtain a leak proof device.

Aluminium backed adhesive film method:

Transdermal drug delivery system may produce unstable matrices if the loading dose is greater than 10 mg. Aluminium backed adhesive film method is a suitable one. For preparation of same, chloroform is choice of solvent, because most of the drugs as well as adhesives are soluble in chloroform. The drug is dissolved in chloroform and adhesive material will be added to the drug solution and dissolved. A custom made aluminium former is lined with aluminium foil and the ends blanked off with tightly fitting cork blocks.

Preparation of TDDS by using proliposomes: -

The proliposomes are prepared by carrier method using film deposition technique. From the earlier reference drug and lecithin in the ratio of 0.1:2.0 can be used as an optimized one. The proliposomes are prepared by taking 5mg of mannitol powder in a 100 ml round bottom flask which is kept at $60-70^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature and the flask is rotated at 80-90 rpm and dried the mannitol at vacuum for 30 min. After drying, the temperature of the water bath is adjusted to $20-30^{\circ}\text{C}$. Drug and lecithin are dissolved in a suitable organic solvent mixture; a 0.5 ml aliquot of the organic solution is introduced into the round bottomed flask at 37°C , after complete drying second aliquot (0.5 ml) of the solution is to be added. After the last loading, the flask containing proliposomes are connected in a lyophilizer and subsequently drug loaded mannitol powders proliposomes) are placed in a desiccator over night and then sieved through 100 mesh. The collected powder is transferred into a glass bottle and stored at the freezing temperature until characterization.

Free film method: -

Free film of cellulose acetate is prepared by casting on mercury surface. A polymer solution 2% w/w is to be prepared by using chloroform. Plasticizers are to be incorporated at a concentration of 40% w/w of polymer weight. Five ml of polymer solution was poured in a glass ring which is placed over the mercury surface in a glass petri dish. The rate of evaporation of the solvent is controlled by placing an inverted funnel over the petri dish. The film formation is noted by observing the mercury surface after complete evaporation of the solvent. The dry film will be separated out and stored between the sheets of wax paper in desiccator until use. Free films of different thickness can be prepared by changing the volume of the polymer solution.

APPROACHES USED IN DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSDERMAL PATCH**Polymer membrane permeation-controlled TDDS**

In this system, the drug reservoir is embedded between an impervious backing layer and a rate controlling membrane. The drug releases only through the rate controlling membrane, which can be micro porous or non- porous. In the drug reservoir compartment, the drug can be in the form of a solution, suspension, or gel or dispersed in solid polymer matrix. On the outer surface of the polymeric membrane a thin layer of drug-compatible, hypoallergenic adhesive polymer can be applied. The rate of drug release from this type of Transdermal drug delivery system can be tailored by varying the polymer composition, permeability coefficient and thickness of the rate controlling membrane.

FIG. 2 POLYMER MEMBRANE PERMEATION-CONTROLLED TDDS.

Adhesive diffusion controlled system:

It is the simplest version of the membrane moderated drug delivery systems. In this system the drug reservoir is formulated by directly dispersing the drug in an adhesive polymer and then spreading the medicated adhesive by solvent casting onto a flat sheet of drug impermeable metallic plastic backing to form thin drug reservoir layer. On the top of the reservoir layer, layers of non-medicated rate controlling adhesive polymer of constant thickness are applied. Drug -in -adhesive patch may be single layer or multi layer. The multi layer system is different from single layer in that it adds another layer of drug-in-adhesive, usually separated by a membrane. Characteristics of drug in adhesive patch may account for improved patient compliance due to ease of remembering once weekly patch application, improved cosmetic acceptance and better adhesion. Marketed devices: Climara®; Nicotrol; Deponit® Here the drug reservoir is formed by homogeneously dispersing the drug solids in a hydrophilic or lipophilic polymer matrix and medicated polymer is then molded into disc with defined area and thickness. This is glued onto an occlusive base plate on the surface of the disc the adhesive polymer is spread along the circumference to form a stripe of adhesive rim around the disc. Advantages of matrix patches include absence of dose dumping, direct exposure of polymeric matrix to the skin and no interference of adhesive. Marketed System: Nitro-Dur®.

FIG. 3 ADHESIVE DIFFUSION CONTROLLED TDDS.

Microreservoir system:

These are considered as combination of reservoir and matrix dispersion type. In this the drug reservoir is formed by first suspending the drug solids in an aqueous solution of water soluble polymer and then dispersing the drug suspension homogeneously in lipophilic polymer, by high shear mechanical force to form unleachable microscopic spheres of drug reservoir. This dispersion is stabilized immediately by cross-linking the polymer chains which produces a medicated disc with constant surface area and thickness. Marketed system Nitrodisc.

FIG. 4 MICRORESERVOIR CONTROLLED TDDS.

FACTORS AFFECTING TRANSDERMAL PERMEABILITY

The principle transport mechanism across mammalian skin is by passive diffusion through primarily the transepidermal route at steady state or through transappendageal route at initially, non steady state. The factors, which affect the permeability of the skin mainly the stratum corneum, are classified into following categories:

1. Physicochemical properties of the penetrant.
2. Physicochemical properties of the drug delivery system.
3. Physicochemical and pathological conditions of the skin.

Physicochemical properties of the penetrant molecule

1. Partition co-efficient: Drug possessing both water and lipid solubilities are favourably absorbed through the skin. Transdermal permeability co-efficient shows a linear dependence on partition co-efficient. Varying the vehicle may also alter a lipid/water partition co-efficient of a drug molecule. The partition co-efficient of a drug molecule may be altered by chemical modification without affecting the pharmacological activity of the drug.
2. pH condition: the effect of pH is mainly on the rates of absorption of acidic and basic drugs, unchanged form of drug has better penetrating capacity. Transport of ionizable species from aqueous solutions shows strong pH dependence.
3. Drug concentration: Transdermal permeability across mammalian skin is a passive diffusion process and this depends on the concentration of penetrant molecule on the surface layer of the skin.

Physicochemical properties of the drug delivery system.

The affinity of the vehicle for the drug molecules:

It can influence the release of the drug molecule from the vehicle. Solubility in the vehicle will determine the release rate of the drug. The mechanism of drug release depends on whether the drug is dissolved or suspended in the delivery system and on the interfacial partition co-efficient of the drug from the delivery system to skin tissue.

Composition of drug delivery system:

Composition of drug delivery system may affect not only the rate of drug release but also the permeability of the stratum corneum by means of hydration.

Enhancement of transdermal permeation:

Release of the drug from the dosage form is less due to the dead nature of the stratum corneum. Penetration enhancers cause the physicochemical or physiological changes in stratum corneum and increase the penetration of the drug through the skin. Various chemical substances found to possess drug penetration enhancing property.

Eg. Dimethyl sulfoxide, Dimethyl formamide, 2-pyrrolidone

Physiological and pathological condition of the skin

Skin age:

Foetal and infant skin appears to be more permeable than adult skin. Percutaneous absorption of topical steroids occurs more rapidly in children than in adults. Water permeation has shown to be same in adults and in children.

Lipid film:

The lipid film on the skin surface is formed by the excretion of sebaceous glands and cell lipids like sebum. and epidermal cell which contain emulsifying agent may provide a protective film to prevent the removal of natural moisturising factor from the skin and help in maintaining the barrier function of the stratum corneum.

Skin hydration:

Hydration of stratum corneum can enhance transdermal permeability. The rate of penetration of salicylic acid through skin with dry and hydrated corneum was measured when the tissue were hydrated, the rate of penetration of the most water soluble esters increased more than that of the other esters.

Skin temperature:

Raising skin temperature results in an increase in the rate of skin permeation. Rise in skin temperature may also increase vasodilation of blood vessels, which are in contact with skin leading to an increase in percutaneous absorption.

Cutaneous drug metabolism:

After crossing the stratum corneum barrier, some of the drug reaches the general circulation in active form and some of this in inactive form or metabolic form, because of the presence of metabolic enzymes present in the skin layers. It was reported that more than 95% of testosterone absorbed was metabolized as it present through the skin.

Species differences:

Mammalian skin from different species display wide differences in anatomy in such characteristics as the thickness of stratum corneum, number of sweat glands and hair follicles per unit surface area.

Pathological injury to the skin:

Injuries to the skin can cause the disturbance in the continuity of stratum corneum and leads to increase in skin permeability.

EVALUATION PARAMETERS:**Interaction studies:**

Excipients are integral components of almost all pharmaceutical dosage forms. The stability of a formulation amongst other factors depends on the compatibility of the drug with the excipients. The drug and the excipients must be compatible with one another to produce a product that is stable, thus it is mandatory to detect any possible physical or chemical interaction as it can affect the bioavailability and stability of the drug. If the excipients are new and have not been used in formulations containing the active substance, the compatibility studies play an important role in formulation development. Interaction studies are commonly carried out in Thermal analysis, FT-IR, UV and chromatographic techniques by comparing their physicochemical characters such as assay, melting endotherms, characteristic wave numbers, absorption maxima etc.,

Thickness of the patch:

The thickness of the drug loaded patch is measured in different points by using a digital micrometer and determines the average thickness and standard deviation for the same to ensure the thickness of the prepared patch.

Weight uniformity:

The prepared patches are to be dried at 60°C for 4hrs before testing. A specified area of patch is to be cut in different parts of the patch and weigh in digital balance. The average weight and standard deviation values are to be calculated from the individual weights.

Folding endurance:

A strip of specific area is to be cut evenly and repeatedly folded at the same place till it broke. The number of times the film could be folded at the same place without breaking gave the value of the folding endurance.

Percentage Moisture content:

The prepared films are to be weighed individually and to be kept in a desiccators containing fused calcium chloride at room temperature for 24 hrs. After 24 hrs the films are to be reweighed and determine the percentage moisture content from the below mentioned formula.

$$\text{Percentage moisture content} = \left[\frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Final weight}} \right] \times 100.$$

Percentage Moisture uptake:

The weighed films are to be kept in a desiccator at room temperature for 24 hrs containing saturated solution of potassium chloride in order to maintain 84% RH. After 24 hrs the films are to be reweighed and determine the percentage moisture uptake from the below mentioned formula.

$$\text{Percentage moisture uptake} = \left[\frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight}}{\text{initial weight}} \right] \times 100.$$

Water vapour permeability (WVP) evaluation:

Water vapour permeability can be determined with foam dressing method the air forced oven is replaced by a natural air circulation oven. The WVP can be determined by the following formula $WVP = W/A$ Where, WVP is expressed in gm/m² per 24hrs, W is the amount of vapour permeated through the patch expressed in gm/24hrs and A is the surface area of the exposure samples expressed in m².

Drug content:

A specified area of patch is to be dissolved in a suitable solvent in specific volume. Then the solution is to be filtered through a filter medium and analyse the drug content with the suitable method (UV or HPLC technique). Each value represents average of three different samples.

Uniformity of dosage unit test:

An accurately weighed portion of the patch is to be cut into small pieces and transferred to a specific volume volumetric flask, dissolved in a suitable solvent and sonicate for complete extraction of drug from the patch and made up to the mark with same. The resulting solution was allowed to settle for about an hour, and the supernatant was suitably diluted to give the desired concentration with suitable solvent. The solution was filtered using 0.2µm membrane filter and analysed by suitable analytical technique (UV or HPLC) and the drug content per piece will be calculated

Polariscope examination:

This test is to be performed to examine the drug crystals from patch by polariscope. A specific surface area of the piece is to be kept on the object slide and observe for the drug crystals to distinguish whether the drug is present as crystalline form or amorphous form in the patch.

Shear Adhesion test:

This test is to be performed for the measurement of the cohesive strength of an adhesive polymer. It can be influenced by the molecular weight, the degree of crosslinking and the composition of polymer, type and the amount of tackifier added. An adhesive coated tape is applied onto a stainless steel plate; a specified weight is hung from the tape, to affect it pulling in a direction parallel to the plate. Shear adhesion strength is determined by measuring the time it takes to pull the tape off the plate. The longer the time take for removal, greater is the shear strength.

Peel Adhesion test:

In this test, the force required to remove an adhesive coating from a test substrate is referred to as peel adhesion. Molecular weight of adhesive polymer, the type and amount of additives are the variables that determined the peel adhesion properties. A single tape is applied to a stainless steel plate or a backing membrane of choice and then tape is pulled from the substrate at a 180° angle, and the force required for tape removed is measured.

Thumb tack test:

It is a qualitative test applied for tack property determination of adhesive. The thumb is simply pressed on the adhesive and the relative tack property is detected.

Flatness test:

Three longitudinal strips are to be cut from each film at different portion like one from the center, other one from the left side, and another one from the right side. The length of each strip was measured and the variation in length because of non-uniformity in flatness was measured by determining percent constriction, with 0% constriction equivalent to 100% flatness

Percentage Elongation break test:

The percentage elongation break is to be determined by noting the length just before the break point, the percentage elongation can be determined from the below mentioned formula. $\text{Elongation percentage} = \frac{L1-L2}{L2} \times 100$
Where, L1 is the final length of each strip and L2 is the initial length of each strip.

Rolling ball tack test:

This test measures the softness of a polymer that relates to tack. In this test, stainless steel ball of 7/16 inches in diameter is released on an inclined track so that it rolls down and comes into contact with horizontal, upward facing adhesive. The distance the ball travels along the adhesive provides the measurement of tack, which is expressed in inch.

Quick Stick (peel-tack) test:

In this test, the tape is pulled away from the substrate at 90°C at a speed of 12 inches/min. The peel force required to break the bond between adhesive and substrate is measured and recorded as tack value, which is expressed in ounces or grams per inch width.

Probe Tack test:

In this test, the tip of a clean probe with a defined surface roughness is brought into contact with adhesive, and when a bond is formed between probe and adhesive. The subsequent removal of the probe mechanically breaks it. The force required to pull the probe away from the adhesive at fixed rate is recorded as tack and it is expressed in grams.

In vitro drug release studies:

The paddle over disc method (USP apparatus V) can be employed for assessment of the release of the drug from the prepared patches. Dry films of known thickness is to be cut into definite shape, weighed, and fixed over a glass plate with an adhesive. The glass plate was then placed in a 500-mL of the dissolution medium or phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), and the apparatus was equilibrated to $32 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The paddle was then set at a distance of 2.5 cm from the glass plate and operated at a speed of 50 rpm. Samples (5- ml aliquots) can be withdrawn at appropriate time intervals up to 24 h and analyzed by UV spectrophotometer or HPLC. The experiment is to be performed in triplicate and the mean value can be calculated.

In vitro skin permeation studies:

An in vitro permeation study can be carried out by using diffusion cell. full thickness abdominal skin of male Wistar rats weighing 200 to 250g. Hair from the abdominal region is to be removed carefully by using a electric clipper; the dermal side of the skin was thoroughly cleaned with distilled water to remove any adhering tissues or blood vessels, equilibrated for an hour in dissolution medium or phosphate buffer pH 7.4 before starting the experiment and was placed on a magnetic stirrer with a small magnetic needle for uniform distribution of the diffusant. The temperature of the cell was maintained at $32 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ using a thermostatically controlled heater. The isolated rat skin piece is to be mounted between the compartments of the diffusion cell, with the epidermis facing upward into the donor compartment. Sample volume of definite volume is to be removed from the receptor compartment at regular intervals, and an equal volume of fresh medium is to be replaced. Samples are to be filtered through filtering medium and can be analyzed spectrophotometrically or HPLC.

Skin Irritation study:

Skin irritation and sensitization testing can be performed on healthy rabbits (average weight 1.2 to 1.5 kg). The dorsal surface (50cm²) of the rabbit is to be cleaned and remove the hair from the clean dorsal surface by shaving and clean the surface by using rectified spirit and the representative formulations can be applied over the skin. The patch is to be removed after 24 hr and the skin is to be observed and classified into 5 grades on the basis of the severity of skin injury.

Stability studies:

Stability studies are to be conducted according to the ICH guidelines by storing the TDDS samples at 40±0.5°C and 75±5% RH for 6 months. The samples were withdrawn at 0, 30, 60, 90 and 180 days and analyze suitably for the drug content.

CONCLUSION

The TDDS review articles provide valuable information regarding the transdermal drug delivery systems and its evaluation process details as a ready reference for the research scientist who is involved in TDDS. The foregoing shows that TDDS have great potentials, being able to use for both hydrophobic and hydrophilic active substance into promising deliverable drugs. To optimize this drug delivery system, greater understanding of the different mechanisms of biological interactions, and polymer are required. TDDS a realistic practical application as the next generation of drug delivery system.

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